

Virtual Senate

Project

Welcome

The
Virtual Senate

of the United States of America

www.VirtualSenate.us

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Surname: _____

E-mail: _____

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Register Virtual Senator:

Name: _____

Surname: _____

State: _____

Birth: _____

E-mail: _____

Political Party: Republican

Democrat

Independent

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Photo requirements:

The Virtual Senate

Virtual Senator

Kathy Fox

Republican Party

Texas

The U.S. Senate

Live:

Virtual Senator

Kathy Fox

Republican Party

Texas

The Bill:

PRIOR PRINTER'S NOS. 693, 1943

PRINTER'S NO. 2117

THE GENERAL ASSEMBLY OF PENNSYLVANIA

SENATE BILL

No. 628 Session of 2005

INTRODUCED BY GREENLEAF, LEMMOND, ORIE, O'PAKE, COSTA, ERICKSON, BRIGHTBILL, MADIGAN, WENGER, RAFFERTY, RHOADES, BOSCOLA, PILEGGI, ROBBINS AND PICCOLA, APRIL 13, 2005

AS AMENDED ON THIRD CONSIDERATION, OCTOBER 3, 2006

AN ACT

1 Amending Titles 18 (Crimes and Offenses) and 20 (Decedents,
2 Estates and Fiduciaries) of the Pennsylvania Consolidated
3 Statutes, providing for the offenses of neglect of care-
4 dependent person and for living wills and health care powers
5 of attorney; further providing for implementation of out-of-
6 hospital nonresuscitation; making conforming amendments; and
7 repealing provisions of 20 Pa.C.S. Chs. 54 and 54A.

8 The General Assembly of the Commonwealth of Pennsylvania

9 hereby enacts as follows:

10 Section 1. Section 2713(e) of Title 18 of the Pennsylvania

11 Consolidated Statutes is amended to read:

12 § 2713. Neglect of care-dependent person.

13 * * *

14 (e) Treatment in conformance with care-dependent person's
15 right to accept or refuse services.--A caretaker or any other
16 individual or facility may offer an affirmative defense to
17 charges filed pursuant to this section if the caretaker,
18 individual or facility can demonstrate through a preponderance
19 of the evidence that the alleged violations result directly
20 from:

Summary: The bill has 5 key points:

1.-----

2.-----

3.-----

4.-----

5.-----

Virtual Senator

Kathy Fox

Republican Party

Texas

Vote the Bill:

Yes

No

Abstain

[Go back](#)

Virtual Senator

Kathy Fox

Republican Party

Texas

>>> Well, I think that this bill is important and may enhance the chances of young Americans to....

>>>

>>>

>>>

>>>

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240 characters.

Virtual Senator

Kathy Fox

Republican Party

Texas

>>> Well, I think that this bill is important and may enhance the chances of young Americans to....

>>>

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Virtual Senator

Michael Foreman

Democratic Party

Tennessee

>>> I totally disagree with this proposal. I have said it since in the start that won't make any difference for the

>>> Americans to get better jobs because...

>>>

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Virtual Senator

Cyndi Mancini

Independent

New Mexico

>>> I have my doubts about the bill I must say! I think it should be discussed even further for its inefficiency and

>>>non clearance. A bill of such importance...

>>>

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Virtual Senator

Nicole Adams

Democratic Party

Virginia

>>> Well, I too have my doubts for this bill ! I have several reasons for my doubt and mainly I am concerned about how..

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Rules of the Virtual Senate:

1. You should only create one profile.
2. You should register only if you are an American citizen.
3. You must be at least 18 years old

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Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
06/04/2021